
CONTINUING EDUCATION OF TEACHERS FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: NECESSARY ACTIONS

Alcemir Horácio Rosa and Prof. Dr. Daniel Nascimento e Silva
Federal Institute of the Amazon Manaus downtown campus, IFAM.

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ABSTRACT:

Education is a collective social process and a right guaranteed to all people. And for it to be effective, adequate training of professionals is necessary. In recent years inclusive education has been gaining ground in debates; in particular, around the continuing education of teachers to provide a more inclusive education. In this way, the present work aimed to analyze the foundations of inclusive education and the way in which continuing education can help in this process. The main documents that support the inclusion were raised, and then a reflection on continuing education was developed. The scientific-technological method (NASCIMENTO-E-SILVA, 2019) was used as a guiding means of the investigation, in which it was possible to: establish the guiding question, organize the data and structure the answers. The work concluded that Brazilian education has not yet managed to establish all the principles of inclusive education, although there have been advances in recent years. The research achieved some results: 1) that continuing education should be a full educational strategy; 2) teachers as mediating subjects; 3) that it is necessary to structure teacher training based on guiding documents; 4) that institutions promote continuing education based on the identification of students with disabilities and disorders; 5) that managers and institutions need to promote the training of teachers for identification, evaluation and referrals; and, 6) teacher training must be aligned with institutional commissions to assist students with specific needs.

KEY WORDS: *Teacher training. Inclusion. Education. Fundamentals of education.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a process of social and collective construction. Therefore, the educational system needs to recognize students and their needs for an effective teaching process. The training of teachers is what can help in the realization of an inclusive education. This is because teachers are the mediating subjects of education, and therefore, they need to undergo adequate continuing education. So that they are able to develop more inclusive practices and methodologies (BLANCO, 2009; SOARES, 2018; COSTA et al. 2018; and, BARANAUSKAS and VALENTE, 2019).

Until the 1980s and 1990s, there was an exclusionary education system. That established a form of teaching that did not include students with any type of disability. And instead of meeting the specifics of the students, it just excluded. However, after the 1990s, schools began to adapt to the global inclusion movement. The vision changed and schools came to understand that they needed to offer the conditions not only for students to enter school environments, but also to succeed and succeed in their educational

path. And in this bias, the institutions, together with the legislation, began to recognize that the initial and continuing education of teachers was something strategic. The continuing education of teachers became linked to the theme of inclusive education. In this sense, this research established a guiding question: What is necessary so that the continuing education of teachers can help in the development of a more inclusive education? The challenges for inclusive education are still great. And the continuing education of teachers is shown as a strategy to achieve better results. In this case, a more in-depth investigation is needed on the legal foundations and how continuing education can help in this process.

Thus, this work took into account that the continuing education of teachers constitutes an effective strategy in the construction of an education for all. In this way, it needs to be supported by legislation and in recognizing the individual specificities of its students: disorders, deficiencies and specific needs.

METHODOLOGY

The work was structured through the scientific-technological method (NASCIMENTO-E-SILVA, 2019). The method allowed, 1) the delimitation of the question; 2) data collection in the academic environment; 3) the organization of the collected data; and, 4) the responses. The guiding question was: What is necessary so that the continuing education of teachers can help in the development of a more inclusive education? The structure of the investigation was organized in: introduction, methodology, development, conclusion and finally, the references. The Introduction was organized in order to approach the theme in a general and problematizing way. The methodology brought the steps by which the work was developed. The development was organized in order to reveal the discussion on the topic. It brought the basis for finding the results presented in the conclusion. The conclusion synthesized and presented the results. Finally, the references brought the scientific bases used.

THE FUNDAMENTALS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The scientific literature allowed an analysis of the foundations of inclusive education. When talking about inclusive education, it is necessary to recognize and understand the foundations that underlie teaching with inclusion, as there are many challenges. It is correct to say that Brazil comes from a history of exclusion, because until the 80s and 90s it was common to have different schools that separated the so-called normal students from those with specific needs. therefore, it is necessary to understand the fundamentals of inclusive education, as well as to understand, put into practice and demand its compliance (UNESCO, 1994; BRASIL, 2008; BRASIL, 1996; BLANCO, 2009; SOARES, 2018; and, SANTOS, 2020).

Inclusive education can be understood as a teaching that integrates, that accepts everyone and that although students have specificities, deficiencies, disorders or specific needs; the school and the society present there are committed to seeking means and strategies to keep students in the classroom, so that they are successful in their educational path (MENDES, 2012).

This topic assumes that only aware of their rights and their fundamental guarantees will the citizen be able to demand the fulfillment of an education that is in fact inclusive. After all, every citizen has the right to an education that recognizes their specificities and the necessary means to break down barriers in the teaching-learning process. And it is based on this argument that we will deal with some of the main foundations of inclusive education.

The Salamanca Declaration of 1994.

This document is considered one of the main basic documents for inclusive education, as it advocates that the education space between so-called normal children and those with disabilities, disorders or specific needs should take place in a common space. After all, it is plurality that makes the environment more constructive. Such a declaration highlights the right of every person to be treated equally, with the same rights; including the right to study together. Each institution should organize "an ongoing network of support should be provided, ranging from minimal help in the regular classroom to additional programs to support in-school learning and expanding, as necessary, to the provision of

assistance given by teachers" (UNESCO, 1994). Salamanca's statement also highlights the importance of the school adapting to the student and not the student adapting to the school as was commonly perceived. It brings a series of rights and guarantees that until then were denied to students, as the school needs to give support and support not only to students with or without disabilities, but to everyone. That is, regardless of whether the student has a disability or not, he has the right to be there and the school has the obligation to propose, seek and offer all the necessary resources for this student to learn and succeed in his educational path.

C.F - Federal Constitution of 1988

The Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988 emphasizes that everyone has the right to education; that is, regardless of being a person with a disability or not, the constitution guarantees every person as a fundamental right. Therefore, this document brings a series of guarantees of rights to people in general, with or without specific needs. For example: right to equality, health, education, culture and sport; establishing that all people should have the right to education and be treated equally. Thus, students with or without disabilities must have the same guaranteed rights, such as the right to education (BRASIL, 2008).

LDB 9394/1996

The LDB - Law of Directives and Bases of National Education is an important document for inclusive education, as it recommends that all students should preferably study together and for those who cannot be kept in a regular classroom, all conditions for that the student has the right to quality education. It guides Brazilian education, so from the moment that the rights of students with specific needs are recognized in the guiding document, as is the case of the LDB, this in a way serves as a guarantee that schools, teachers and education systems adapt to these regulations and start looking for the best ways to deliver inclusive education (BRASIL, 1996).

The Declaration of Guatemala - 1999

This declaration gave people with disabilities the recognition of equal rights with other people and the guarantee that there should be no form of discrimination. All citizens must have their rights guaranteed, regardless of whether or not they are people with specific needs. There should be no form of inequality or discriminatory treatment, after all, everyone is equal, respecting the specifics of each one (UNESCO, 1987).

CONTINUING EDUCATION OF TEACHERS FOR INCLUSION

The foundations of inclusive education serve to understand that although people are different; it takes an education that meets the specifics to guarantee the conditions of access, permanence and success of our students. Continuing teacher education for inclusion is a way of recognizing that the school needs to adapt to the specific needs of students and not let students be forced to adapt to the school's routine. It needs to articulate the training proposal with the institutional reality and with the identity of its students and, in this way, seek to identify the students' deficiencies, the specific needs and the disorders they may have. Through permanent education, it is possible to have practices and methodologies resignified; to propose measures, solutions and adaptations that can meet and provide conditions for the student to have a quality education and that really help in the formation of a citizen, critical and reflective identity in which so much is discussed today within schools.

Thus, this work addressed the need to understand some of the main disorders that are identified within school environments, so that the topic can be discussed and help in the search for an adequate discussion about it.

MAIN EDUCATIONAL DISABILITIES AND DISORDERS

Continuing teacher education can help achieve results for inclusive education. However, it is first necessary to recognize what are the elements of this education. Table 1 presents the main

deficiencies and disorders present in school environments. Institutions need to propose training that takes care of identifying students with specific needs and only then establish strategies that can really help in the teaching-learning process. (SANTOS, 2020).

Table 1
Main deficiencies and disorders identified in the school environment
Intellectual disability
Impairment of mental, intellectual or sensory abilities. Thus, it is necessary that the school adapts to the reality of these students and makes use of means, equipment and skills that can instigate these students to face such difficulties and barriers.
Visual impairment
Limitation or total loss of vision. Students may be totally blind or have low vision where the disability prevents them from following classes and school routine. It is necessary for the school to establish some strategies or methods that help the student to acquire skills by other means, such as: speech or class narration, among other possibilities that recognize their specific condition and that provide conditions.
Physical disability
Any disability that prevents the student from moving regularly; being, for example: due to bad training or any incident that makes it impossible for him to enjoy his locomotor skills.
Pervasive developmental disorders
Autism
A disorder that causes difficulty interacting with people around you. This disorder causes difficulty in interacting with both the teacher and their peers. It also causes difficulty in the construction of knowledge, as it causes non-interaction. It is necessary for the school to develop strategies that can include the student and seek appropriate means to help overcome learning barriers. Continuing education is an appropriate strategy to achieve the student's teaching-learning process.
Asperger's syndrome
It is a subsystem of autism; however, it is differentiated because it is only identified over the years, as the symptoms are quite mild. That is, it is something much more difficult to be diagnosed and that takes longer to be noticed. In this sense, the school should seek to have a well-prepared team with adequate continuing education to identify the characteristics of this disorder.
Reet's syndrome
Almost exclusively female, it is of genetic origin and causes a disorder in the neurological system, so the student has great difficulty in interacting and developing logical reasoning. Thus, the child cannot follow the contents and the development of a class in a traditional way. The intervention of specialized professionals is necessary to give a correct accompaniment in the classes. In this sense, the school needs to offer an inclusive education, in which specialized professionals are available to accompany and assist in the development of students.
Childhood disintegrative disorder
This disorder is also known as childhood psychosis. In this disorder, what occurs is a sudden return of psychological or motor functions. Usually, the person begins to regress in a matter of days and weeks, losing skills, such as: mobility, speech, interpersonal relationships, among other skills. All of this suddenly.
Specific functional disorders
Specific functional disorders are groups of disorders that cause a series of difficulties, among which the most common are: dyslexia, dysgraphia, dysorthography, dyscalculia and attention and hyperactivity disorder.
Dyslexia is usually configured by a lack of student attention that prevents the student from being able, for example, to read a complete text, develop logical reasoning or transcribe a word correctly. It is a disorder that many schools and professionals still have difficulty identifying, so continuing education can contribute a lot in this process.

Dysgraphia is directly related to the student's writing disorder. cannot transcribe a word with its accents or spelling correctly.
Dysorthography , on the other hand, is related to the lack of orientation of the student's writing, in which he writes words wrongly or out of standard.
Dyscalculia is a disorder that is directly related to the math question or calculation, the student who has dyscalculia has great difficulty in establishing mathematical reasoning.
Attention hyperactivity disorder is when the student has great difficulty in establishing a reasoning and maintaining attention on something. It has a wide range of attention and mood and the consequences of this are usually that the student is unable to maintain attention and concentration on a certain subject or content.

Table 1 presents the main deficiencies and disorders found in educational environments. This information is strategic so that the continuing education of teachers can develop teachers for an inclusive service and, as mediators, can help to create a more welcoming educational environment (SOARES, 2018; BLANCO, 2009; COSTA et al. 2018; BORTOLI et al. CASTAMAN, 2020; and, BARANAUSKAS and VALENTE, 2019).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The research allowed us to identify the necessary actions so that the continuing education of teachers can help in the development of a more inclusive education. The necessary actions are: 1) continuing education to be developed as a strategy for transforming educational environments; 2) teachers as mediating subjects in school institutions; 3) structuring teacher training based on documents that guide inclusive education; 4) promote permanent education based on the identification of students with disabilities and disorders; 5) that managers and institutions promote the training of teachers for the identification, evaluation and referral of students with disabilities and disorders; and, 6) teacher training must be aligned with institutional commissions to serve students with some type of disability; monitor the teaching-learning process of students with specific needs.

Finally, the work concludes that Brazilian education has not yet been able to put into practice all the principles of inclusive education within school institutions and that despite advances, it is still necessary for institutions and managers to seek the necessary means, methodologies and strategies. That schools and education are truly inclusive.

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